

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ZEBON****FIRST NAME: JOSEPH****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACA-401D QUIZ

1. The kind of data sources that would help the researcher to keep up with current research, find out other points of view, and develop models for one's research and analysis are:

- All three sources of data are equally important.
- Tertiary sources of data.
- Primary sources of data are firsthand.
- Secondary data sources.¹**

2. The author-date style citation requires

¹ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 36.

- Notes and bibliography.
 - Place a superscript number at the end of the sentence and explain that superscript number as a note, providing the author, title, and publication facts, including relevant page numbers.
 - Citing it once writing its source in full in the note and citing the exact text subsequently will accommodate the notes.
 - Using parenthesis instead of superscript numbers, author, date, and page numbers are placed right after the reference in the text, and all sources will be listed in the reference.²**
3. What does it mean to organize and plan carefully for dissertation research to be successful?
- Keep all other issues of life aside and focus on the dissertation.
 - Create and operate a physical, mental, and intellectual workspace, creating a system for organizing and managing your work by developing a writing routine and keeping records of information, managing time, saving all drafts, thinking, and saving all information.³**
 - Read all the time.
 - Read and keep all information in one's head without taking notes.

² Turabian et al., 142.

³ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, Fourth edition (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 110–32.

4. What is research within the context of ACA-401D?
- Ethical considerations, submissions, and funding detailed methodology.
 - A detailed study outline, methodology feasibility, identified problem, and analysis.
 - A process of systematic inquiry to answer a question that the researcher and others want to solve.⁴**
 - Topic, introduction, research questions, bibliography.
5. How do you reference a single-authored book using the Turabian Author-Date citation style?
- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (parentheses), Title (quotation mark), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
 - Author's first name Author's last name. Edition. Date. Title (underlined). Editor(s)/Translator(s). Place: Publication Press.
 - Author's Last Name, Author's First Name. Year of Publication. Title of Book: Subtitle of Book. Place of Publication: Publisher's Name.⁵**
 - Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (in parentheses), Title, Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
6. How is a quotation written in line with UK English about quotation marks?
- Quotation marks are used for both.

⁴ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 19.

⁵ Turabian et al., 222.

- The quotation starts with inverted commas; the quotation within this is in quotation marks.
- The quotation begins with quotation marks; the quotation within this is in inverted commas.**⁶
- Both parties use inverted commas.
7. Tick the correct response below that indicates the appropriate scholarly method for a qualitative dissertation.
- Focus groups, one-on-one interviews, case studies, qualitative observation, and ethnographic research.
- Briefly describe the methods, equipment, procedures, the limitations encountered, sample collection, and data analysis.
- Research sample, research design, method of data collection, data collection methods, data analysis and synthesis, ethical consideration, trustworthiness issues, limitation, and delimitation.**⁷
- Design justification, design paraphrase, data collection and analysis, study design.
8. What is the appropriate date format for writing for the EU audience?
- Day month year.
- Day-Month-Year.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington DC: Euclid University), 2024), 31.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 439–80.

Day Month (spelt in full) Year.⁸

Month, Day, year.

9. What is the difference between notes-bibliography and author-date styles in citation formats?

The notes-bibliography style uses in-text citations, while the author-date style uses footnotes.

Both styles use footnotes for citation.

The notes-bibliography style uses footnotes, while the author-date style uses in-text citations.⁹

Both styles use in-text citations for citation.

10. What are the main components of the initial parts of a dissertation? Indicate the correct sequence.

Title, Supervisory Committee Page, Dedication, Acknowledgments, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, Biography, and Abstract.¹⁰

Title, Prefects, Dedication, Acknowledgments, Table of Contents, List of Tables, List of Figures, belief, and Abstract.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, Eighth edition (European Commission, 2021,) 39.

⁹ Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 177–79.

¹⁰ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 24–26.

- Title, Dedication, Supervisory Committee Page, Acknowledgments, List of Tables, Table of Contents, List of Figures, Abstract, and Biography.
- All of the above.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition (Washington DC: Euclid University), 2024.
- European Commission. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth edition. European Commission., 2021.
- Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.
- Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University Of Chicago Press Editorial Sta. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.